

FAIR PUBLISHING SELF-ASSESSMENT GRID
OpenEdition Journals platform Example

Dataset name

OpenEdition Journal data

Dataset summary

Data sources

Data is produced through Lodel by publishers and editors
 Data can be updated by the users (not fully controlled by the organization)
 Documentary units' have distinct levels: content, issue and collection levels

Data expressions

Is raw data the content of the Lodel database (as it is used to create the HTML expression)?
 Other expressions/outputs: TEI OpenEdition, PDF, ePUB
 Metadata

Comments

Different properties exist depending on the types (proper to Lodel software):

- A volume contains publications (issues, columns, annual columns); A Documentary unit contains contents;
- Different types of contents (article, column, editorial, review, ...);
- Annexe files types can contain data (xls, csv, sound, image, video files).

Not all the different types are available in all the different expressions (TEI, pdf, epub).
 Question: Should the review consider object types that don't correspond to specific data types (subpart, section, site, directory, etc.)?

FAIR PRINCIPLES REVIEW

Findability

FAIR principle F1

(Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier

FAIR implementations

FAIR enablers

FAIR challenges

Objects:

- DOI (prefix 10.4000): available only for some data (depending on the types and publishers' wishes)
- Issue for resources with multiple DOIs
- Handles generated by [Isidore](#) harvesting platform (not retrieved by OE)

Persons: a few Orcid are available

Organizations: a few IDs from Crossref Funding registry.

- OAI identifiers exist for all documentary units but they are not PIDs
- All documentary units are identified in the information system though the concatenation (internal purposes only): Platform+SiteName+ID

Objects:

- Some data without any PID
- DOIs may exist for data published on another platform that we do not retrieve.
- Handles assigned by Isidore are not retrieved.

Persons: Contributors are not linked to registries.

FAIR principle F2

Data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)

<i>FAIR implementations</i>	<i>FAIR enablers</i>	<i>FAIR challenges</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Metadata available in the OAI-PMH repository (could be richer)• Available formats in the OAI-PMH repository: DublinCore, DublinCoreTerms, METS	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Rich metadata is available in the information system; could be also extensively integrated in the OAI repository.• In OAI, metadata available only for certain types of contents (types subpart, heading, and news are missing)	

FAIR principle F3

Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe

FAIR implementations

FAIR enablers

FAIR challenges

In the OAI repository:

- ID OAI
- DOI when available

Some data without any PID (see F1)

FAIR principle F4

(Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource

<i>FAIR implementations</i>	<i>FAIR enablers</i>	<i>FAIR challenges</i>
<p>OpenEdition Search interface (search.openedition.org):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• only a selection of data is available (some types are excluded),• metadata are not complete. <p>(Meta)data is also searchable in other directories (e.g. Isidore platform harvests OE's OAI repository)</p>	<p>No public API available yet, but all the information is available through the search software (SolR)</p>	

FAIR PRINCIPLES REVIEW

Accessibility

FAIR principle A1

(Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol

FAIR implementations

- HTML: accessible via the DOI
- Metadata: accessible via the OAI identifier

FAIR enablers

FAIR challenges

Some data without any PID (see F1)

Other communication protocol than OAI-PMH and HTTP has to be identified (in case it's useful)

FAIR principle A1.1

The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable

FAIR implementations

- HTTP for the data
- OAI-PMH for the metadata

FAIR enablers

FAIR challenges

FAIR principle A1.2

The protocol allows for an authentication and authorisation procedure, where necessary

<i>FAIR implementations</i>	<i>FAIR enablers</i>	<i>FAIR challenges</i>
<p>All protocols are open, but not all allow for authentication.</p> <p>Protocol used for restricted access contents:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• TCP/IP for contents requiring authentication (TEI version's case) <p>Other protocols used where authentication is not required:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• HTTP for open access contents• OAI-PMH for the metadata		<p>Lack of a tool dedicated to the management of authentication and authorization processes.</p>

FAIR principle A2

Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available

FAIR implementations

FAIR enablers

FAIR challenges

No

No records for the deleted data

FAIR PRINCIPLES REVIEW

Interoperability

FAIR principle II

(Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.

FAIR implementations

FAIR enablers

FAIR challenges

Structured formats/language:

- Data: TEI
- Metadata: Dublin Core, METS

No semantic layer is implemented

FAIR principle I2

(Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles

FAIR implementations

In some journals, editors use disciplinary controlled vocabularies (e.g. French [Pactols](#)).

FAIR enablers

Some disciplinary controlled vocabularies (e.g., [JEL](#)) could be integrated with thesaurus management tools

FAIR challenges

For most of the journals, no controlled vocabulary is used.

FAIR principle I3

(Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data

FAIR implementations

In OAI repository:

- is part of (for parts of documentary units)
- relation with OpenAIRE accessright field

Some links with translations

FAIR enablers

- Information about Citation and Cited-by is stored, but not disseminated
- Link with translations not recorded in the OAI repository
- on-going project: OE Review of Books

FAIR challenges

FAIR PRINCIPLES REVIEW

Reusability

FAIR principle R1

(Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes

FAIR implementations

FAIR enablers

FAIR challenges

(see above F2)

(see above F2)

(see above F2)

FAIR principle R1.1

(Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license

<i>FAIR implementations</i>	<i>FAIR enablers</i>	<i>FAIR challenges</i>
<p>Licenses are defined by journals and not by documentary units, except in a few cases.</p> <p>The license is not defined according to the different expressions, the same license applies for all (HTML, PDF, ePUB).</p>	<p>License should be distinct for each expressions and the information be added to the database and to the TEI</p>	<p>No clear provision to allow for the text and data mining exception (acknowledged by French law “Loi pour une république numérique”)</p> <p>The license applied to the documents is not always clear.</p> <p>The license has sometimes been declared by the journal retroactively, and has therefore uncertain value.</p>

FAIR principle R1.2

(Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance

FAIR implementations

FAIR enablers

FAIR challenges

Internal creation process not described (can be created through Lodel, outsourced digitization, etc.)

FAIR principle R1.3

(Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

FAIR implementations

FAIR enablers

FAIR challenges

I1: (meta)data meet community standards for textual contents, including TEI.

I2: Fewer (meta)data meet disciplinary communities standards.

FAIR PUBLISHING - REVIEW GRID

Dataset name

Name of the reviewed dataset (journals or articles collection)

Dataset summary

Data sources

Describe how the dataset is being produced in order to better identify the scope of the FAIRification.

Specify which operator creates the dataset and for which part.

It is useful to indicate which part is

- created automatically or by individuals
- if data and metadata are created independently or not,
- if data and metadata are created by different operators or different tools,
- if modifications to the dataset are possible or if it exists in a non editable final version,
- etc.

Data expressions

Describe in which different formats or states the resource exists, in order to identify on which one the FAIRification process should or could apply.

	<p>Part of the dataset are also the metadata, which can also appear in different formats for different operators. These various metadata formats or schemas should be specified here.</p>
Comments	<p>Record here any information useful to understand the dataset, i.e. the publications and their metadata, in case some of their specificities may have an impact on the FAIRification.</p> <p>This section can include mentions about the different types of publications (e.g., paper, reviews, etc.), the specific practices in terms of metadata (e.g., identifiers for any person, or only for some roles, etc.)</p>

FAIR PRINCIPLES REVIEW

Findability

Findability addresses the way digital resources can be searched and found on the web. Like all the FAIR principles, Findability takes into account both humans and machines. This principle mostly considers minimal ways to make digital data findable, without evaluating in detail the quality or richness of data and metadata.

FAIR principle F1

(Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier

Generic guidelines

The F1 principle concerns the identifiers of resources in the digital environment. Like any other identifiers, the digital identifiers have to be unique. However, differently than other kinds of identifiers, like for instance the identifiers of printed books in a local archive, they need to be also global and persistent. Globality and persistence refer here to the digital environment: the identifier has to be unique at the level of the internet, and ensure persistence throughout the changes of URLs, servers, etc. Additionally, the persistent identifier, or PID, is more efficient when it contains a resolution link to the original resource.

There are various ways to create such persistent identifiers. The most common one is to use the services of registration agencies specialized in the creation and management of PIDs. This is the case, for instance, of Crossref or Datacite, both producing Digital Objects identifiers, or DOIs. However, these are only specific cases which imply a payment for the service. The technology behind is also available independently and for free, like with the PIDs obtained through [handle.net](https://www.handle.net/), which is the software used and enhanced by Crossref.

As suggested by the principle, metadata records themselves can be assigned PIDs. This is particularly useful and justified when metadata records are complex and access to the data itself is limited. PID's assignment to metadata records is usually under the responsibility of the databases' managers, as it is a feature that has to be implemented at the global level of an information system.

Publishers guidelines

In the context of publishing, Crossref DOIs are the most commonly used, although Datacite's DOIs, mostly used for research data, can also be used for publications. On the other hand, traditional identifiers for publication, like ISSNs or ISBNs, are not strictly speaking PIDs. They are unique and global, but they are not persistent in the sense of directly addressing the potential changes of platforms or URLs: the digital persistence has to be implemented by the publishing service itself, for instance integrating the ISBN or ISSN into a permanent URL (called PURL). In fact, ISBN and ISSN do not entail a resolution link to the resource.

PIDs are usually managed automatically through the publishing tool or service used by the publisher, with costs covered or not by the infrastructure. The FAIRification challenges in this case thus strongly depends on this tool or service: does it integrate the feature of producing PIDs, which type of PIDs, for any publication type, for articles and also for journals?

PIDs for metadata records in the case of publications is definitely not a priority, especially in the case of Diamond Open Access journals where contents are easily accessible. Identifiers, not PIDs, of metadata records are sometimes automatically created through the use of OAI-PMH repositories, but only for data management purposes, with no direct impact on findability.

FAIR review objective for F1

The FAIR review for F1 is meant to assess the current situation, in order to evaluate, even approximately, what PIDs are currently used, what is their current coverage of the resources' collection, how the coverage can be extended, and what currently limits the extension.

FAIR implementations

FAIR enablers

FAIR challenges

<i>To fill with the list of current implementations that fulfill this FAIR principle</i>	<i>To fill with the list of current implementations that could enable this FAIR principle with some adjustments</i>	<i>To fill with the list of current obstacles to the implementation of this FAIR principle</i>
<i>FAIR principle F2</i>		
<u>Data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)</u>		
<p style="text-align: center;">Generic guidelines</p> <p>F2 principle explicitly tackles metadata and its richness. Metadata is the information about data (i.e. about a resource, a publication, a dataset, etc.) that allows for its discovery in the digital environment. Metadata is indeed a term specific to the digital assets and corresponds to an information that may be understandable for a human, but which is first and foremost formatted for the machines.</p> <p>Metadata are of different types: descriptive, structural, administrative. F2 principles mostly considers descriptive metadata, meaning the information that facilitates discovery and often corresponds to information traditionally recorded already in the print context (e.g. author’s name, publication date, etc.). Such metadata facilitates discovery insofar as it brings up in searching activities results that were not previously known nor looked for. Descriptive metadata are indeed used to build filters and search queries on databases.</p> <p>The “richness” of descriptive metadata is highly dependent on the context: the resource described, the place where it is stored, the service allowing for the search, the targeted audience, etc. However, even if the richness is not always defined by a set of minimal metadata, any community of practice tendentially recognize a certain number of metadata as minimal for a good discoverability. Principle R1 gives a bit more details on the information that can ensure a higher richness of metadata.</p>		

Publishers guidelines

Publications have been described for centuries with additional information that helped to find them (when one knows what to search for, and potentially discover them (when one finds unexpected useful results). This work conducted by libraries and publishers was easily integrated within the digital environment in the form of metadata. This set of information constitutes what can be considered as the minimal metadata for publications. It entails mainly: title, authors' names, publication date, publisher, rights, language, subjects, abstract. This list is not exhaustive and depends on the context, but is usually the set of information required from any publishing or discovery service dedicated to academic publications.

It can be further extended with complementary metadata, for instance: identifiers for authors (e.g. VIAF, ORCID) or for organizations (e.g. ROR), formatted licensing information (e.g. Creative Commons licensing), etc. The minimal set can also be further enriched with additional metadata: geographic or historical coverage, contributors besides the authors, etc. Theoretically, metadata can be easily enriched, but the enrichment can be practically challenging, if not counter-productive in case metadata's generation and validation is too complex.

In the FAIR context, metadata enrichment, as it concerns recurrent operations of information formatting, should always be measured, not only to its importance for discoverability, but also to the actual possibility of either supporting the enrichment on the long term, or even automating this enrichment process.

FAIR review objective for F2

The FAIR review should in this case evaluate which of the minimal metadata for publications are already and properly recorded, if enhancements of the existing metadata are possible (for instance adding identifiers to an existing list of authors), and if there are constraints or limitations to either improve or extend the metadata already recorded.

<i>FAIR implementations</i>	<i>FAIR enablers</i>	<i>FAIR challenges</i>
<i>To fill with the list of current implementations that fulfill this FAIR principle</i>	<i>To fill with the list of current implementations that could enable this FAIR principle with some adjustments</i>	<i>To fill with the list of current obstacles to the implementation of this FAIR principle</i>

FAIR principle F3

Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe

Generic guidelines

Although directly dependent on the data they describe, metadata are a distinct digital asset, concretely: they are most of the time stored in a distinct file. F3 principle addresses this distinction by requiring that data and metadata do have a connection through the identifier of the data, especially in the prospect of machine queries. The identifier considered here should be the PID, if it exists.

In some cases, data and metadata can be stored in different places, or they can have distinct access rights. Recording the identifier of the data within metadata may seem to be obvious, but it is absolutely necessary in the digital environment in order to indicate which metadata is linked to which data. In this way, it becomes for instance possible to run a query based on this identifier and collect back the data and its corresponding metadata.

More importantly, the identifier of the data has to be "explicitly" included in the metadata, as the F3 principle says. This actually means that the identifier should not only be stored as any piece of information, but as a qualified information, i.e. with addition of semantics. The metadata should record the identifier explicitly tagging it as "identifier", so that machines and humans know its nature.

This is normally done through the use of metadata schemas, which often do include a field "identifier" (e.g., in the Dublin Core metadata schema: <https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/dcmi-terms/#http://purl.org/dc/terms/identifier>). In that sense, the F3 principle is closely related to principles I1 and I3 that recommend the use of standards for metadata.

Publishers guidelines

For publications, the F3 principle mostly means to record the identifier of a publication or a journal in the corresponding metadata file. The metadata should therefore record the ISSN, which is one valid identifier, and also the actual PID, like for instance a DOI.

Concretely, the F3 principle is addressed through the use of an appropriate metadata schema, like explained above. Most of the time, the implementation and management of such metadata schemas is handled by publishing systems and their administrators, rather than by the publishers themselves. For instance, in the case of the storage of metadata records in an OAI-PMH repository, the minimum Dublin Core metadata schema provides a field for the identifier of the resource, and it is usually filled automatically by the publishing system itself. However, publishers managing their content themselves should check that their system does apply this principle.

FAIR review objective for F3

The F3 principle is closely related to F1, i.e. to the existence of a PID. The objective here is to check if all existing PIDs for the collection are well recorded in the metadata, and, in case not all the assets have a PID (as defined in F1), if they have at least an identifier recorded in the metadata files.

<i>FAIR implementations</i>	<i>FAIR enablers</i>	<i>FAIR challenges</i>
<i>To fill with the list of current implementations that fulfill this FAIR principle</i>	<i>To fill with the list of current implementations that could enable this FAIR principle with some adjustments</i>	<i>To fill with the list of current obstacles to the implementation of this FAIR principle</i>

FAIR principle F4

(Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource

Generic guidelines

The F4 principle complements and closes the Findability principles: after listing the main elements enabling the findability of an asset (information allowing for unique identification, descriptive metadata allowing for search, and clear links between data and metadata), it specifies where and how these elements can be used, that is to say the infrastructure that holds data and metadata.

The data and the metadata need indeed to be searchable, meaning not stored on a local disk or repository only as an archive, but within an infrastructure allowing at least for information retrieval, if not direct and full data retrieval.

Many services either offer such searching features, openly or not, or reuse the searching features of other services. The “searchable resource” can therefore correspond to various types. It can be an OAI-PMH repository, allowing for a limited number of queries. It can be a platform offering searching or filtering features in its own collection, like for instance DOAJ. It can be also an aggregator, collecting information from various places (i.e. OAI-PMH repositories, platforms, etc.), like BASE or OpenAire. It can also be a more simple crawler with more limited filtering features, like for instance Google Scholar.

While the design and management of such searching resources is under the responsibility of database administrators, it is under the responsibility of the data creator to ensure that its contents are stored at least in one of these searching resources.

Publishers guidelines

In the context of academic publishing, the F4 principle both concerns the service where the publications are stored in the first place, but also, more globally, where the publications are referenced.

While the availability of contents and metadata on a home-made public website is a way to follow the principle, better and broader dissemination is achieved through the referencing of these contents on larger databases. Such databases not only do have requirements that increase data and metadata quality, but they also ensure, through their service, a broad dissemination and findability.

Just to mention generic tools or services addressing principle F4 for academic publications, we can give a few examples: OAI-PMH repositories, Pubmed, DOAJ, OpenAire, BASE, GoTriple, CORE, Dimensions, ERIH PLUS, etc. However, many others exist in specific thematic fields, geographic areas, linguistic contexts, etc.

FAIR review objective for F4

The FAIR review in this case checks where the data and metadata are searchable, whether any data or metadata is available or only a part of them, if the contents are searchable in only one service or are also referenced in many others, and what are the various ways to search for them (manually and/or automatically and/or massively).

<i>FAIR implementations</i>	<i>FAIR enablers</i>	<i>FAIR challenges</i>
<i>To fill with the list of current implementations that fulfill this FAIR principle</i>	<i>To fill with the list of current implementations that could enable this FAIR principle with some adjustments</i>	<i>To fill with the list of current obstacles to the implementation of this FAIR principle</i>

FAIR PRINCIPLES REVIEW

Accessibility

Accessibility, in the context of FAIR, does not refer to the legal access or usage license, but to the technical and practical access to a resource or its metadata record. It considers indeed rather mechanisms, protocols, services allowing, even under specific legal conditions, access to the considered assets.

FAIR principle A1

(Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol

Generic guidelines

A1 is a generic accessibility principle, closely related to F1. It illustrates and confirms the need for PIDs: persistent identifiers are indeed the easiest and most common way, both for machines and the humans using them, to access contents or their metadata.

The standard communication protocol required by A1 principle should be intended here very broadly. Basically, A1 principle means that “anyone with a computer and an internet connection can access at least the metadata”, as says the original documentation on FAIR principles. This documentation mentions as an example the TCP/IP protocol, i.e. the protocol supporting the internet, which became a *de facto* standard.

In the internet context, beyond the searching web engines, which provide filtering of all the information available on the internet, the main way to collect, organize and manage digital resources is to use their PIDs. The filters, or other searching features, are indeed based on metadata which is collected itself, in the first place, through the PIDs.

A1 principle aims at ensuring that data, metadata and their PIDs belong to a stable communication infrastructure, and are therefore accessible, at least potentially.

Publishers guidelines

For academic publications, A1 principle refers both to the existence of PIDs and to the availability of contents and metadata through well-established digital communication protocols. The main objective of this recommendation is to avoid having contents stored locally on personal devices, or through complex and *ad hoc* protocols.

The recommendation can be addressed in various ways, for instance: publishing contents in HTML format, storing the metadata on institutional databases or through a local repository relying on a shared technology like OAI-PMH (Open Archive Initiative - Protocol for Metadata Harvesting).

FAIR review objective for A1

The FAIR review should here list where the contents and their metadata are accessible, and according to which protocol or technology. The FAIR review can only consider the primary publishing instance of contents and metadata; it is not necessary here to list all the services referencing this primary publishing instance.

Note that A1 principle does not have to be addressed specifically: it can be addressed implicitly through the following A1.1 principle.

<i>FAIR implementations</i>	<i>FAIR enablers</i>	<i>FAIR challenges</i>
<i>To fill with the list of current implementations that fulfill this FAIR principle</i>	<i>To fill with the list of current implementations that could enable this FAIR principle with some adjustments</i>	<i>To fill with the list of current obstacles to the implementation of this FAIR principle</i>
<i>FAIR principle A1.1</i>		

The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable

Generic guidelines

A1.1 principles extends A1 principle by specifying the nature of the digital communication standard. The protocol should not only technically allow access to data and/or metadata, it should also be widely shared, free and open. The principle excludes both proprietary and local set-ups, as they both limit universal access. The implementation of the protocol (given that economical conditions of the implementer concretely allow for it) should not require high or any cost, and should instead rely on open source technology that are either widely known, or easy to master.

Publishers guidelines

In the broad context of FAIR, which considers research data in general, the recommended protocols are, for instance, HTTP or FTP. For academic publications, especially in the case of Diamond Open Access journals, FTP shouldn't be considered as a valid way to give access to the journals' contents.

The use of HTTP, on the contrary, represents a perfectly valid way to implement A1.1 principle. The HTTP protocol can be used to serve either HTML contents, or PDFs files, or other publication formats. For the metadata, a valid and widely used protocol is OAI-PMH. Indeed, the availability of metadata on search engines and databases does not necessarily ensure that the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable, like is the OAI-PMH protocol.

FAIR review objective for A1.1

The FAIR review should list the protocols used to access the data (i.e. the journal's contents) and the metadata (i.e. the bibliographic information). In this way, the review of A1.1 principle can address implicitly the A1 principle.

FAIR implementations

FAIR enablers

FAIR challenges

<i>To fill with the list of current implementations that fulfill this FAIR principle</i>	<i>To fill with the list of current implementations that could enable this FAIR principle with some adjustments</i>	<i>To fill with the list of current obstacles to the implementation of this FAIR principle</i>
<i>FAIR principle A1.2</i>		
<u>The protocol allows for an authentication and authorisation procedure, where necessary</u>		
<p style="text-align: center;">Generic guidelines</p> <p>The principle A1.2 represents a technical illustration of the more generic principle applying to research outputs in the context of Open Science: “research outputs should be as open as possible, as closed as necessary”. Research outputs can indeed be in closed access in some cases, for ethical, legal, or contractual reasons. FAIR principles, in particular, do not comprise any requirement about the openness of the contents, but rather about the technologies and the infrastructure used to access the contents. In that sense, research outputs that are not open or free can still be perfectly FAIR compliant.</p> <p>In the case of A1.2 principle, the accessibility is evaluated with consideration to the access rights management and their technical implementation. It explicitly mentions the Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure, or AAI. AAI corresponds to a variety of frameworks and services ensuring the automated identification of the user (individual or organization), and the verification of its access rights. Typically, in the case of a research output accessible only to researchers of a given university, AAI will first check if the user is recorded in the list of the organization’s members and if its status within the organization matches the access rights set for this research output.</p> <p>There are many ways, characterized by many different perimeters and contexts, to implement AAI processes. There is no need to list them here. The A1.2 is matched when the access protocol allows for AAI or AAI-like processes, whatever the technology or infrastructure used.</p>		

Publishers guidelines

In the context of academic publishing, the management of access rights mostly concerns the contents. Furthermore, in the case of Diamond Open Access journals, authentication and authorization are by definition unnecessary. Nevertheless, even in the case of Diamond Open Access, the contents may be fully accessible only in specific formats, for instance: access to HTML is open, but access to PDF requires authorizations.

In all cases besides full and free access to the contents, the A1.2 principle requires that the method used to make the verification is clear both for humans and machines. The only condition is that, when specific access rights are set, it is always possible to check if a given user matches these access rights. Usually, the AAI infrastructure or feature is managed at the level of the publishing service, or even at the level of the infrastructure including the publishing service. Publishers that are not managing themselves the accesses can check with their IT team if the FAIR principle is met.

To be noted also that in some cases, even the metadata can be in closed access, when, for instance, it is recorded in a proprietary service having its own access rights. Even in this case, i.e. accessing the metadata under conditions, a clear method and information should exist about the authentication and authorization process.

FAIR review objective for A1.2

The FAIR review should list the cases where some assets, data or metadata, is accessible under conditions: in these cases, the reviewers have to ensure an AAI procedure does exist. Naturally, if both contents and their metadata are all fully and freely available, the principle is not applicable.

<i>FAIR implementations</i>	<i>FAIR enablers</i>	<i>FAIR challenges</i>
<i>To fill with the list of current implementations that fulfill this FAIR principle</i>	<i>To fill with the list of current implementations that could enable this FAIR principle with some adjustments</i>	<i>To fill with the list of current obstacles to the implementation of this FAIR principle</i>
<i>FAIR principle A2</i>		

Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available

Generic guidelines

The A2 principle contains a recommendation somehow defining minimal accessibility: whenever the data itself is not available anymore, at least the metadata describing it should be preserved. Digital data, like physical objects, can disappear, either by design, or by accident. Additionally, maintaining metadata records is by far less costly than maintaining full datasets. Ensuring that the metadata will still be preserved allows the users, humans or machines, to have information about the dataset, its content, its purpose, its generation, etc. The metadata record itself, or the PID of the dataset may indeed still be cited in some publications: the metadata record should therefore still be maintained, and possibly also contain information about the dataset deletion.

In this case also, like in all Accessibility principles, the FAIR principle implementation is in most cases under the responsibility of the publishing service or the infrastructure administrator.

Publishers guidelines

Metadata preservation in the case of academic publishing more specifically relates to depublished, or republished contents. Either the deletion of the contents on a given service, or its transfer to another service, requires that the metadata still exist, and that it records the information about the missing content.

Publishers usually do not manage such requirements themselves, and they should check it with the help of their IT team.

FAIR review objective for A2

The FAIR review should in this case verify how the information about deleted, depublished, or removed contents are managed.

FAIR implementations

FAIR enablers

FAIR challenges

To fill with the list of current implementations that fulfill this FAIR principle

To fill with the list of current implementations that could enable this FAIR principle with some adjustments

To fill with the list of current obstacles to the implementation of this FAIR principle

FAIR PRINCIPLES REVIEW

Interoperability

Interoperability, strictly speaking, refers to the operations that are reciprocally possible between machines and their various forms or contents (e.g., between services, tools, data, metadata, etc.). In the context of FAIR, it corresponds to the use of formats, schemas, or shared practices that allow machines to exchange data and metadata.

Interoperability thus refers to any standard applied to data and/or metadata that is sufficiently shared for any operator to understand, handle, and use it. In the case of FAIR interoperability, it concerns mostly the provision of a “semantic” layer that adds some meaning about the data and metadata that machines and humans can then understand.

FAIR principle I1

(Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.

Generic guidelines

Principle I1 introduces the notion of “knowledge”, especially as it appears in the digital environment. In fact, besides the strictly technical definition of interoperability, which can be achieved through the use of common, stable, and well-defined formats (e.g., PNG, PDF, etc.), interoperability of research outputs is also reached through knowledge and its representation. A table of values, or the picture of a painting require additional information to be meaningful and usable: what the values do measure, at which time and location were they collected, when the painting was produced, by whom, when the picture of the painting was taken, etc.?

In the digital environment, as anything is only a series of bits, the additional information provided by the metadata is a necessity and a rather common practice to bring appropriate knowledge about the described data. However, it is still not

sufficient to fully address interoperability objectives. Indeed, metadata should not only describe the data as accurately as possible, it should also do it in a formalized way: not only declaring that a name recorded in metadata is the name of the painter of the picture, but declare it in a formal way recognized by other persons and services.

At a first level, formalization can take the form of a list of terms that several actors agree upon and use to describe similar objects (for instance, bibliographic information about publications). In the digital context, another level of formalization allowing for more interoperability is knowledge representation. Intended broadly, knowledge representation refers to a wider organization of meaningful concepts, now connected between themselves through specific and explicit relationships, like in taxonomies or ontologies. Such representations often rely on specific programming languages, for instance: RDF, OWL, SKOS, etc.

With regard to principle I1, which does not recommend the use of any technology or methodology, the objective is to ensure the highest interoperability by: using a formalized language, sharing it among many operators and services, formatting it for automated use by the machines, and finally, if possible, connecting this formal, shared, and machine-compliant language, with other similar objects thanks to knowledge representation.

Publishers guidelines

In the publishing context, interoperability can be reached through standards for knowledge representation applying either to the data, or to the metadata. These standards add most of the time formalized semantics to the considered assets.

In a first simple way, technical interoperability is ensured with the use of standard formats: for instance, contents in PDF files, metadata in XML files. However, on one hand, PDF is only a *de facto* standard, furthermore proprietary, therefore not fully interoperable as it requires specific tools to be handled; on the other hand, XML is in itself only a language, with too generic a grammar to bring accurate understanding of its content.

For what concerns the contents, additional understanding, and therefore additional interoperability, is brought with more detailed standards: the TEI or the JATS XML specifications, in particular. Basically, TEI or JATS are only a list of terms applied to blocks of the content that correspond to widely accepted intellectual objects (e.g., paragraph, author, title, abstract,

etc.). They represent a specific grammar and dictionary of the XML language. These standards allow therefore for richer and more explicit information about the contents' structure that is then understandable by humans and machines as well.

For what concerns the metadata, knowledge representation works essentially in the same way, only with different standards applying to a different set of information. Metadata can indeed be included in the TEI or JATS files directly, and retrieved this way. Metadata can also rely on other standards. The most common one for publishing is Dublin Core Metadata Initiative, which can be expressed in XML, and contains a list of formalized terms corresponding to generic bibliographic information. Other similar standards can be used for other purposes: METS standard is used for instance to handle the management of metadata about complex objects (e.g., various files pertaining to the same publication).

The generation and management of the standard files is dependent on the tool or service used, and they are usually under the responsibility of the infrastructure administrators. It is however important for the data producer to know if and which standards are used for its content, both to ensure that its content is actually interoperable, and to potentially improve their interoperability.

FAIR review objective for I1

The FAIR review of I1 should at least provide a list of the standards used to describe data and metadata. An additional useful step is to examine to which extent the standards are being used and evaluate if some improvements would be possible (e.g., Dublin Core exists in various flavours and contains a long list of possible metadata: some of them may be deemed useful to add).

<i>FAIR implementations</i>	<i>FAIR enablers</i>	<i>FAIR challenges</i>
<i>To fill with the list of current implementations that fulfill this FAIR principle</i>	<i>To fill with the list of current implementations that could enable this FAIR principle with some adjustments</i>	<i>To fill with the list of current obstacles to the implementation of this FAIR principle</i>
<i>FAIR principle I2</i>		

(Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles

Generic guidelines

Principle I2 addresses primarily vocabularies and their FAIR features. Without entering into too detailed terminological questions, vocabularies, or more precisely controlled vocabularies, can be considered as a minimal type of knowledge representation. Controlled vocabularies can be of various types and apply to various notions. The most common examples of controlled vocabularies apply to topics, but they can also apply to data types, document types, job positions, professional competences, etc.

The minimum form of controlled vocabulary is a flat list of verified and stable terms. These terms can be used to create an index of topics, for instance. Other more complex forms of controlled vocabularies exist, for instance thesauri, which contain a list of concepts, corresponding to various synonym terms, and connected with each other through logical relationships (e.g. hierarchy, similarity, inclusion, etc.).

Controlled vocabularies for topics are the main focus of FAIR principles for two reasons: they are one of the main features to find contents and classify them globally; they are also closely related to disciplinary areas and therefore often defined and used locally. They are both a powerful tool and a challenge for interoperability.

This is why the FAIR principles recommend not only to use controlled vocabularies, but to connect them through a formal knowledge representation, i.e. exposing them in broader ontologies able to represent the knowledge of more than one area. Principle I2, adds a more specific recommendation in that prospect: making the controlled vocabularies themselves FAIR.

A FAIR vocabulary contains PIDs for its concepts, ensures accessibility of its contents, makes use of standards, and provides clear rules about its contents' reusability. The controlled vocabulary thus becomes a FAIR object itself that can be handled easily by machines and potentially be connected with other FAIR controlled vocabularies.

Publishers guidelines

Academic publications use different kinds of controlled vocabularies. Besides controlled vocabularies for document types and similar vocabularies applying to generic objects, we often find vocabularies used for topics that are more specific. They can either correspond to broad thematics identified by publishers in any field, or vocabularies proper to a given community. These two types can also be combined to describe one single resource.

Proper to the publishing field, we can mention the BISAC subject headings list. A similar vocabulary often used in libraries is the Library of Congress Subject Headings (LCSH). Disciplinary vocabularies are also well-developed: Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) for medicine, European Language Social Science Thesaurus (ELSST) for social sciences.

The building of well-accepted controlled vocabularies is a major community effort and their integration within publishing systems is also a demanding task. The recommendation of I2 principle to make such objects FAIR themselves adds another complexity.

In this context, the responsibility of the publishers is only to use and promote existing controlled vocabularies, instead of creating new ones locally, and to evaluate their interoperability, i.e. examine if they are widely used, apply technical standards, and follow FAIR principles.

FAIR review objective for I2

Principle I2 should first bring to list the controlled vocabularies used to describe the publications' topics, then to evaluate their global interoperability, and finally, where possible, to assess their level of FAIRness.

<i>FAIR implementations</i>	<i>FAIR enablers</i>	<i>FAIR challenges</i>
<i>To fill with the list of current implementations that fulfill this FAIR principle</i>	<i>To fill with the list of current implementations that could enable this FAIR principle with some adjustments</i>	<i>To fill with the list of current obstacles to the implementation of this FAIR principle</i>

FAIR principle I3

(Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data

Generic guidelines

Principle I3 addresses the topic of interconnection between resources. It recommends having relationships between resources clearly established and recorded as machine-actionable information. Such information is sometimes described as “qualified reference”, i.e. a reference that contains semantics clarifying the type of the relation, for instance: “version of”, “part of”, “cited by”, etc.

The first case where the I3 principle should be applied is the relationship between the data file and its metadata file, even more so if the data exist in several versions and the metadata itself is versioned. Qualified references are also useful when a resource is based on the aggregation of several datasets, or when a dataset is processed in various steps using different tools or services.

Qualified references are supported by other FAIR principles. They should indeed contain at least the record of the other resource’s PID, relying in this way on principle F1. Furthermore, some standards for descriptive metadata include the possibility to indicate qualified references, thus following I1 principle. The already mentioned Dublin Core metadata schema, for instance, includes the possibility to record the following qualified references: isPartOf, isReferencedBy, isReplacedBy, etc. In fact, the most used metadata schemas usually contain a number of metadata dedicated to qualified references.

Publishers guidelines

In the context of publishing, one the first examples of reference useful to record are related to the traditional components of a publication: relationship between chapters and a monograph, between a monograph and a collection, etc. Qualified references can also be used when different versions of a single paper are published in different places. In the case of data papers, the relationship between the paper and the related dataset is essential to the reading and understanding of the paper, and therefore an information to record in the metadata.

Metadata schemas or models often used in the publishing context, like the aforementioned Dublin Core or the OpenAire guidelines, offer the possibility to indicate useful qualified references. Nevertheless, qualified references offer many possibilities and their implementation can be complex, especially with broad collections of items. The importance of the qualified references should therefore be carefully evaluated to decide whether or not to record them.

Even in the case where publishers do not handle the metadata records directly, they are the ones able to decide the value of recording specific qualified references and they are also the ones able to communicate that specific information. In that sense, publishers can contribute to the implementation of principle I3.

FAIR review objective for I3

The FAIR review for I3 principle should aim at listing the qualified references currently recorded in the metadata and their quality. Additional qualified references, identified through existing metadata schemas or models, can also be examined to decide about their potential future implementation.

<i>FAIR implementations</i>	<i>FAIR enablers</i>	<i>FAIR challenges</i>
<i>To fill with the list of current implementations that fulfill this FAIR principle</i>	<i>To fill with the list of current implementations that could enable this FAIR principle with some adjustments</i>	<i>To fill with the list of current obstacles to the implementation of this FAIR principle</i>

FAIR PRINCIPLES REVIEW

Reusability

Reusability principles somehow represent the final goal of the FAIR principles, which Findability, Accessibility, and Interoperability principles make possible. It addresses the concrete aspects of FAIR principles for research outputs: allowing for data's reading, processing, and aggregation, not only for data's discovery.

Reusability includes a cumulative perspective, where the volume of data produced can be aggregated into bigger datasets; an ethical perspective, by giving the possibility to check data scientific quality and originality; and finally an economical perspective, ensuring to not duplicate the work effort by making datasets reusable.

FAIR principle R1

(Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes

Generic guidelines

The R1 principle extends and specifies the F2 principle. The F2 principle mostly envisions discovery: providing minimal metadata that will facilitate data discovery, even without ensuring that the discovery will end up with very accurate answers to a specific query. R1 principle, on the contrary, seeks to increase data or metadata richness, so that more complex queries can receive more appropriate answers.

Although "richness" is difficult to evaluate, it is sometimes considered that the best practice is to not presume what would be the user's needs, and therefore to provide as much contextual information as possible, for any potential reuse. This might be particularly important in the field of natural or experimental sciences, where not only the variables measured and their measures are important, but the entire context of the observation or experiment.

The fact remains that a richness so openly defined can only be an horizon: no one, precisely, can assume what information a future user may need, and therefore, without more information about the user's expectations, some information will necessarily be missing. Furthermore, enriching minimal metadata for discovery with more contextual and more specific metadata is time consuming, with benefits that remain by nature hypothetical.

For this reason, R1 implementation should aim at providing as much information as possible considering the most common practices and needs of a given community. The enrichment of the minimal metadata beyond these boundaries should be carefully evaluated and planned, and possibly rely on the use of automatic enrichment tools, provided that the quality of their results is satisfying.

Publishers guidelines

Strictly speaking, the first reusability method in the case of text publishing is, since quite some time, simply the reading. Written texts, and even more so printed texts, are meant to be reused through the reading and the memorization. In that sense, making published contents available through the Open Access model, and especially the Diamond Open Access model, providing metadata that ensure high discovery, essentially addresses the reusability principle.

However, in the digital environment, the description of publications can be extended in two different directions: considering publications as textual content, or as research data.

In the first case, the main objective remains the reading by humans, but the discovery of the content is improved through more refined queries. While minimal metadata for publications is well known and covered by the main metadata schemas, additional information can be provided to increase metadata richness. Suggestions for a potential enrichment of minimal metadata can be extracted from a quick comparison between the Dublin Core 15 main elements (<https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/dces/>) and the OpenAire more extensive guidelines (https://openaire-guidelines-for-literature-repository-managers.readthedocs.io/en/v4.0.0/application_profile.html).

In the second case, textual contents can be processed as research data, meaning aggregated into bigger datasets for automated and massive analysis. In that case, a richer description of authoring, provenance, scope, topics, funding, etc. can

be of high importance. Such description would necessarily go beyond Dublin Core 15 elements, whose goal is mostly to provide bibliographic information.

To be noted that the metadata generation is directly dependent on the publishing tool, and that the addition of new metadata may require updates of the publishing tool itself.

FAIR review objective for R1

The FAIR review for R1 should evaluate the current richness of the metadata according to the community’s common needs and practices, considering also the metadata eventually included in structured formats (e.g., XML TEI or JATS). The review should in addition review the most used metadata schemas for publication and identify in them which additional metadata could increase the publications’ reusability and be easily implemented.

<i>FAIR implementations</i>	<i>FAIR enablers</i>	<i>FAIR challenges</i>
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FAIR principle R1.1

(Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license

Generic guidelines

The R1.1 principle recommends adding a “clear and accessible” license about the possible usage of the data. Indeed, the absence of clear information about possible use of the data and the metadata does not mean that they are by default free to use.

In order to allow for specific use cases, the principle does not require that the data and neither the metadata are open, only that the licensing information is clear and accessible. To be clear, the license should remain simple and correspond to widely known use cases. To be accessible, the license should be found and accessed easily by humans, but actually, as much as possible, by machines. This means that the license should be findable in the metadata, and possibly correspond to a well-identified type of license, that a machine can interpret and understand easily.

In that sense, widely used and clearly defined open licenses seem preferable to specific and complex proprietary licenses. In the prospect of reusability, the most permissive licenses are obviously preferable. Many open licenses are applicable to any research outputs: research data, academic publications, software, etc. While Creative Commons (<https://creativecommons.org/>) can be used for any research output, other open licenses exist for specific objects, like GNU (<https://www.gnu.org/licenses/gpl-3.0.en.html>) or MIT (<https://opensource.org/license/mit>) licenses for software, or Open Database license for data (<https://opendatacommons.org/licenses/odbl/summary/>).

Furthermore, license can be applied to data, but also to metadata, especially when data is in restricted access: the metadata can in this case be exposed with a more permissive license than the data itself.

Publishers guidelines

For academic publications, the contents' possible usage is firstly determined by the legal authorship rights management. The legal framework for authorship rights may depend on the national context. In all cases, however, open licensing can complement without contradiction the legal authorship rights, by specifying only some specific accepted usage of the contents.

Even in the case of Open Access publishing, and even if it is Diamond Open Access, the explicit mention of a license is necessary so that humans and machines understand what usage can be made of the contents. For contents in Open Access, one of the most common and most efficient license is offered by the Creative Commons options.

Note that licensing may be distinct for the text produced by the authors, for the contents cited within the publications, and even for the metadata. In the case of publication in various formats also, the license selected can be different. Metadata that

is fully open and free to use should also be explicitly tagged as such: in the case of Creative Commons licenses, this corresponds to the CC-0 license, where “zero” means that there are no restrictions of any kind about usage.

Best publishing practices recommend that the license is applied not only at the journal level, but more importantly at the article level. License should be easily accessible together with the content, which means it has to be recorded not only on a webpage or within the paper itself, but attached within metadata. In fact, most common licenses like Creative Commons also allow to identify the license in a formalized way that can easily be recorded in metadata and understood by machines.

FAIR review objective for R1.1

The FAIR review should check if any licensing is applied on the contents, if yes, if it is open or not, accessible or not, at which level the license is applied, and where and how the licensing information is recorded. This review of principle R1.1 should allow to evaluate what is already implemented, what could support better implementation, and what are the main obstacles to implementation of the principle R1.1.

<i>FAIR implementations</i>	<i>FAIR enablers</i>	<i>FAIR challenges</i>
<i>To fill with the list of current implementations that fulfill this FAIR principle</i>	<i>To fill with the list of current implementations that could enable this FAIR principle with some adjustments</i>	<i>To fill with the list of current obstacles to the implementation of this FAIR principle</i>

FAIR principle R1.2

[\(Meta\)data are associated with detailed provenance](#)

Generic guidelines

The R1.2 principle is self-explanatory: it recommends specifying the dataset’s provenance. In the academic digital context, provenance refers not only to the owner or to the instance responsible for the first publication of the dataset, but also to the entire process of generation. Especially in the case of research data, the reuse is highly dependent on this generation

process: how the data was collected or aggregated and by whom, who should be credited for which part of the work, what was the research project or the funder that supported the dataset creation, which collection, cleansing, organization, analysis processes did undergo the data, etc.? All this information can help humans and machines understand what is the precise nature of the dataset, if it answers their needs, and whether they can or not reuse it.

Like in all the other FAIR principles, it is recommended to make such information as machine-actionable as possible, i.e. to formalize it as much as possible for potential automated queries and analysis. One typical example of an efficient formalization of provenance information has been established by the W3C organization and is called the “PROV data model” (<https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-dm/>).

Publishers guidelines

In the context of academic publishing, the first and main provenance information are about the authorship and ownership. Such information can however be extended and detailed. Authorship can include all the contributors to the publication, from translation to copy-editing. Authorship could also include a mention about the use of generative AI, even if it was only partial. Ownership can also be specified, by mentioning what is the legal entity, beyond the authors, responsible for the publication and the funder of the research project that led to the publication.

Authorship and ownership should in addition, for machine-actionability and quality of the information purposes, follow principle F1 about the use of PIDs: for example, specifying the Orcid and VIAF identifiers for persons, or ROR identifier for organizations.

Moreover, the process of creation of the publication can also be described. The publishing process is always a complex process and provenance information can inform humans and machines about the publication’s nature. Provenance can give details, beyond the intellectual creation of its content, about the tools used for the publication’s generation as a digital object available for reuse in research projects. This is particularly true for publishing objects like data papers: the information about data creation and analysis can be described in the paper itself, but also more formally in the metadata.

It can be difficult for publications to identify a state of the publication that is an actual “primary source” or “raw data”, then transformed several times before the final published state - and it can also be of limited interest. However, it can be useful to

indicate the major transformation steps. For instance, it may be useful in the prospect of reuse to indicate if the working file was a .doc file, then processed to produce an XML file: the mention of these different final formats and the tools used give important information about the generation process of the publication.

FAIR review objective for R1.2

The review for principle R1.2 should first seek to ensure that authorship and ownership information are clear, complete, and machine-actionable. In a second step, the review can try to list the main versions and formats of the publications, as well as the tools and technologies used to produce the final version. It becomes then possible to decide whether it is useful and feasible to record formally this generation process.

<i>FAIR implementations</i>	<i>FAIR enablers</i>	<i>FAIR challenges</i>
<i>To fill with the list of current implementations that fulfill this FAIR principle</i>	<i>To fill with the list of current implementations that could enable this FAIR principle with some adjustments</i>	<i>To fill with the list of current obstacles to the implementation of this FAIR principle</i>

FAIR principle R1.3

(Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

Generic guidelines

While several FAIR principles contain generic recommendations related to the digital infrastructure, the R1.3 principle explicitly targets needs related to specific communities. The term “community” allows to consider varying perimeters: a community can refer to a discipline, a topic, a practice, a data type, a research project, etc. It offers therefore a certain margin of interpretation of principle R1.3, but also a potential complexity, as an individual or an organization can then belong to several communities. The term “standard” should itself be intended broadly: it can be an official standard (e.g., the ISO standards), or a policy widely followed, or even simply a *de facto* common best practice.

The main goal of principle R1.3 is to ensure that, whenever local or specific standards or norms are applied to either data or metadata, they should still be shared practices with other actors of a given community. If PID systems mentioned in F1, for example, apply to the global digital infrastructure and concretely exist in a limited number, other practices more limited in scope could still be valid FAIR implementations if: 1/ they follow the more generic FAIR principles whenever possible; 2/ they are shared amongst a high number of operators.

The domain-relevant standards can apply to data. For instance, there are standards for images like IIF (International Image Interoperability Framework) which can be used by various communities, even beyond the boundaries of specific disciplines. The domain-relevant standards can also apply to metadata, and this is in particular the case with metadata schemas and controlled vocabularies for topics. In these last two cases, both the amount of users and the level of FAIRness of the schema or the controlled vocabulary used, make them valid FAIR implementations, even if these standards are specific to a community.

Publishers guidelines

For academic publishing, domain-relevant standards or best practices can concern data, i.e. the publication's contents. Publications are usually published using widespread formats like PDF. However, as a proprietary format, PDFs are not as interoperable as publishing dedicated formats, like XML JATS or TEI. In any case, besides these examples, any exotic or local publishing format should be avoided.

For what concerns metadata, domain-relevant standards can be proper to either publications, or scientific fields. The metadata for publications are mostly inherited from the library and publishing tradition and constitute a well-established standard.

There is indeed a set of minimal metadata that is both available on the publishing tools, and recommended by the databases for academic publications. There are nevertheless some minor differences in terms of requirements from one database to another. A comparison between, for instance, the requirements from OpenAire, DOAJ and BASE can give a good idea of what is the minimum metadata expected for publications, with OpenAire being slightly more demanding (6 mandatory metadata) and BASE being more open (1 mandatory field and many only optional).

Domain-relevant metadata can also correspond to scientific fields. These are most of the time related to the topics of the publications (e.g. archaeology, linguistics, physics, mathematics, etc.). The topics can be defined globally by the publishers (e.g., BISAC), or by the scientific community. Domain-relevant metadata can also exist for objects proper to specific fields (e.g. genes, languages, etc.). It is up to the publishers to decide which domain-relevant metadata they should apply.

To be noted that the publishing domain standards are also set up by policies. In particular, important policies for Open Access publications can be found in Plan S. The Diamond Open Access Standard also contains recommendations applying to Diamond Open Access journals. While these policies contain broad recommendations about publishing, many of them are of technical nature and aligned with the FAIR principles.

FAIR review objective for R1.3

The R1.3 principle review should list the current domain-relevant standards used by the publisher, whether the domain corresponds to publishing in general, or to a specific scientific area. The review should also list which other domain-relevant standards for either the data or the metadata could be applied in order to improve reusability of the contents.

<i>FAIR implementations</i>	<i>FAIR enablers</i>	<i>FAIR challenges</i>
<i>To fill with the list of current implementations that fulfill this FAIR principle</i>	<i>To fill with the list of current implementations that could enable this FAIR principle with some adjustments</i>	<i>To fill with the list of current obstacles to the implementation of this FAIR principle</i>

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